

JAVASCRIPT TILIDA O'ZGARUVCHILAR VA MA'LUMOTLAR TIPLARI.

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning usullari, o'zgaruvchilarni nomlash qoidalari va o'zgaruvchilar qamrovi (scope) haqida ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, o'zgaruvchi, var, let, const, scope.

Аннотация: В данной диссертации представлена информация о методах объявления переменных в языке программирования JavaScript, правилах именования переменных и области видимости переменных.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, переменная, var, let, const, область видимости.

Abstract: This thesis provides information on the methods of declaring variables in the JavaScript programming language, the rules for naming variables, and the scope of variables.

Keywords: JavaScript, variable, var, let, const, scope.

JavaScript tilida o'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning 4 xil usuli bor bo'lib quyidagilar kiradi: var, let, const va hech narsa ishlatmasdan.

O'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, o'zgaruvchilar bo'lib, ular **var** kalit so'z bilan e'lon qilinadi:

```
var x = 5;
var y = 6;
var z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolni **let** kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilishga misol keltiramiz.

```
let x = 5;
let y = 6;
let z = x + y;
```

O'zgaruvchilar

Identifikatorga biriktirilgan literal o'zgaruvchi deb ataladi, ulardan dasturning keyingi qismida foydalanishi mumkin.

JavaScript sizga **uchta** oddiy turdagi ma'lumotlar bilan ishlashga imkon beradi.

1. **Raqamlar.** Masalan 123, 120, 50 va boshqalar.
2. **Belgi, satrlar.** Masalan «Bu matn qatori» va boshqalar.
3. **Boolean.** Masalan rost yoki yolg'on.

JavaScript-da ma'lumot turlari

Javascript Reserved Keywords		
var	function	if
else	do	while

for	switch	break
continue	return	try
catch	finally	debugger
case	class	this
default	false	true
in	instanceof	typeof
new	null	throw
void	width	delete

O'zgaruvchidan foydalanish uchun uni avval e'lon qilish kerak. JavaScriptda buni 3 xil usulda amalga oshirish mumkin: var, let yoki const kalit so'zlari orqali. Bularning har biri turli maqsadlarda ishlatiladi.

var orqali e'lon qilish ES2015 gacha var o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilishning yagona yo'li bo'lgan.
var a = 0

Agar var so'zini qo'yishni unutsangiz, siz e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchiga qiymat berayotgan bo'lasiz va natija siz kutgandek bo'lmaydi. Zamonaviy muhitlarda yoki strict rejimi yoqilgan bo'lsa, yuqoridagi holatda xatolik yuz beradi. Eski muhitlarda (yoki strict rejimi o'chirilgan bo'lsa), o'zgaruvchini initsializatsiya qiladi va global obyektga biriktirib qo'yadi. Qo'shimcha ma'lumot uchun, initsializatsiya — o'zgaruvchiga dastlabki qiymatni o'zlashtirish jarayoni.

o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilganda uni initsializatsiya qilmasangiz, u undefined qiymatini o'zlashtiradi va unga yangi qiymat bermaguningizcha bu holatni saqlab turadi.

```
var a // typeof a === 'undefined'
```

Bir o'zgaruvchini bir necha marta e'lon qilishingiz mumkin, bunda oldingisi inkor qilinadi:

```
var a = 1
```

```
var a = 2
```

Bir qatorda bir nechta o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishingiz ham mumkin:
var a = 1, b = 2

Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchilar:

```
x = 5;
```

```
y = 6;
```

```
z = x + y;
```

O'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilish uchun var, let va const kalit so'zlari ishlatiladi. var kalit so'zi 1995 yildan 2015 yilgacha barcha JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. let va const kalit so'zlari 2015 yildan boshlab JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. Agar siz eski browser ishlatsangiz u

holda var kalit so'zidan foydalanishingiz zarur bo'ladi. const kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun PI ni qiymati o'zgarimas bo'lib uni const bilan e'lon qilishimiz mumkin. O'zgaruvchi nomlari harflar (A-Z va a-z), raqamlar (0-9), pastki chiziq () va dollar belgisi (\$) dan iborat bo'lishi mumkin. O'zgaruvchi nomlari raqam bilan boshlanmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchi nomlari JavaScriptda maxsus ma'noga ega bo'lgan kalit so'zlardan foydalanib bo'lmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchi nomlari katta-kichik harflarga sezgir. O'zgaruvchi nomlari ma'noli va tushunarli bo'lmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchilar qamrovi (scope) bu o'sha o'zgaruvchining ko'rinish nuqtasi va o'sha nuqtada unga murojaat etish imkoniyatini anglatadi.

Xulosa:

Ushbu tezisda JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilar mavzuini tahlil qildik. Biz o'rganib chiqdik ki, JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilar nima, ularni nomlash qoidalari nima va ularning turli xil scopelari nima. Biz shuningdek, var, let va const kalit so'zlari orqali o'zgaruvchilar bilan ishlashni ham ko'rib chiqdik.

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